
Plan Overview

A Data Management Plan created using DMPonline

Title: REDMIX

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Project abstract:

The debate on mixed-race people is gaining momentum, and the Red Sea – located at the crossroads of Africa and the Middle East, of the Mediterranean Sea and the Indian Ocean – stands as a privileged venue to investigate mixedness. Focusing on a timeframe (1800s-2000s) marked by increasing mobilities and mixed-race unions and offspring (e.g. Afro-Arabs, Afro-Asians, Euro-Africans), REDMIX investigates the roots and routes of mixed-race people and groups through a bottom-up, long-term, and interdisciplinary perspective, to create an online database accessible through a digital archive about mixedness in the Red Sea. African and Middle Eastern Studies have examined the Red Sea, its mobilities, and its entanglements, but mixedness has remained marginal in their thematic and methodological debate. Critical Mixed Race Studies has explored mixedness as a broad concept referring to individuals of mixed descent, yet without ever digging into case studies from the Red Sea. Thus, an extensive analysis of when, how, and why mixed-race people and groups have negotiated their position at political and social turning points in the history of the Red Sea is still lacking. REDMIX aims to fill this methodological and knowledge gap by overcoming the partitioned approach to the Red Sea and promoting a perspective centred on mixed-race people. The project intertwines African, Middle Eastern, and (Critical) Mixed Race Studies; brings together a rich corpus of archival and oral sources scattered across Europe, Africa, and the Middle East; resorts to the digital humanities; and contributes to the conceptual framework of mixedness by applying global microhistory and comparatively investigating different case studies through synchronic and diachronic analyses. As the first comparative investigation into the history of mixedness in the Red Sea, REDMIX will take an active part in the mission of writing a more inclusive history of the area, one that firmly establishes the centrality of mixed-race people.

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REDMIX

Summary

Project Acronym

REDMIX

Project Number

101124725

Provide a dataset summary

REDMIX will use the following sources:

CATEGORY	TYPE	SUB-TYPE	LOCATION
Textual	Published	Books, articles, reports, demographic statistics (i.e. census), administrative investigation	Libraries and research institutes
Textual	Unpublished	Archival sources	National archives and private archives*, religious archives
Audio-video	Published	Documentaries, radio programs, recorded interviews	National and institutional archives, broadcasting archives
Audio-video	Unpublished	Home videos	Private archives*, religious archives
Visual	Published	Historical photographs	Social media, libraries, and research institutes
Visual	Unpublished	Historical photographs	National and institutional archives, religious archives, private archives*

* In the case of using private archives, compliance with the GDPR - Regulation 2016/679 (see Section 2 - "Making data openly accessible") has been ensured, and consent has been obtained.

REDMIX will produce the following data:

CATEGORY	TYPE	FORMAT ONGOING	FORMAT PRESERVATION	EXPECTED SIZE	LICENCE	OPEN/ RESTRICTED	REPOSITORY
Textual	Reports	.doc	.pdf	<0,5 GB	CC BY	Restricted*	Zenodo
	Journal articles	.doc	.pdf	<0,5 GB	CC BY	Open	Zenodo
	Books	.doc	.pdf	<0,5 GB	CC BY	Open	Zenodo
	Consent form template	.doc	.pdf	<0,1 MB	CC BY	Open	Zenodo
	Consent form (compiled)	.doc	.pdf	<0,1 MB	CC BY	Restricted*	Zenodo
Audiovisual	Recording of workshops	.mp4	.mp4	<5 GB	CC BY	Open	Zenodo
Visual	Photos	.jpeg	.pdf	<5 GB	CC BY	Open	Zenodo
Geospatial	Multilayer maps	dataset of separated files (i.e. .shp, .csv format)	dataset of separated files (i.e. .shp, .csv format)	<0,5 GB	CC BY	Open	Zenodo
Tabular	Database of sources	.xls	.csv	<5 GB	CC BY or CC0 with credits	Open	Zenodo
	Bibliographies	.rdf	.rdf/.pdf	<1 GB	CC BY	Open	Zotero
Software **		.php/.js	.php/.js	<2 GB	GNU GPL 2.0	Open	GitHub
Data Management Plan		.pdf	.pdf	<0,1 MB	CC BY	Open	Zenodo

* These resources are restricted because they contain sensitive data, in compliance with the GDPR - Regulation 2016/679 (see Section 2 - "Making data openly accessible").

** The modifications to the DSpace code and the software for building the website will be released as open-source on GitHub.

All ethical aspects related to data and participant involvement have been detailed and approved in the Ethics document prepared following the grant award, along with the templates for informed consent forms.

For resource management, when possible, open-source software will be used, such as:

- QGIS - for mapping;
- Dragon Pro - for the transcriptions of audiovisual materials;
- Emovo and Essentia - for emotional state analysis of audiovisual materials;
- DSpace and Metadatics - for database organization;
- Gramps - for genealogical research;
- Zotero - a library will be set up to include the project's outcomes, such as:
 - journal articles;
 - books;
 - bibliographies of key publications relevant to the project.

For genealogical research, in addition to the previously mentioned open-source software Gramps, GenoPro is used, proprietary software for which a license is already available for all the REDMIX team members.

FAIR data and resources

1. Making data findable

To make the project outputs Findable, a REDMIX collection has been created in Zenodo, corresponding to the URL <https://zenodo.org/communities/redseamixedness>

All the outputs will be identified by the DOIs assigned by Zenodo.

All the records in Zenodo will be described according to the Zenodo metadata schema compliant with the DataCite schema (see <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>)

Zenodo tackles the F/FAIR principle as follows (see <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>):

To be Findable:

- **F1:** (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier

- A DOI is issued to every published record on Zenodo.
- **F2:** data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
 - Zenodo's metadata is compliant with [DataCite's Metadata Schema](#) minimum and recommended terms, with a few additional enrichments.
- **F3:** metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes
 - The DOI is a top-level and a mandatory field in the metadata of each record.
- **F4:** (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource
 - Metadata of each record is indexed and searchable directly in Zenodo's search engine immediately after publishing.
 - Metadata of each record is sent to DataCite servers during DOI registration and indexed there.

All data generated by the project is copied and stored, with the version control number to Zenodo. Data is thus findable in two ways, through data repository and through REDMIX's own online database, managed with DSpace, accessible through a digital archive about mixedness in the Red Sea.

At this stage, DSpace is not yet configured. REDMIX is leveraging on FAIRsharing (<https://fairsharing.org/>) and the RDA metadata standard catalog (<https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>) to identify the most suitable metadata schema and other standards.

In DSpace, each item is assigned a handle as its unique identifier.

Currently, hosting costs are estimated at around €1500 per year, though they may vary depending on storage requirements for the material to be archived and maintenance expenses.

2. Making data openly accessible

The REDMIX Zenodo Community will display project outputs according to the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary".

The only restricted outputs are the reports and the consent forms compiled. This is because both cases contain sensitive data (as defined by Article 4, paragraphs 13, 14, and 15, and Article 9 of the GDPR - Regulation 2016/679) concerning the project team and the involved users. However, this data will be available for the team members and the project audit.

As previously shown, REDMIX will use standard formats for long-term preservation.

Zenodo tackles the A/Accessible principle as follows (see <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>):

- **A1:** (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol
 - Metadata for individual records, as well as record collections, are harvestable using the [OAI-PMH](#) protocol by the record identifier and the collection name.
 - Metadata is also retrievable through the public [REST API](#).
- **A1.1:** the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
 - See point A1. OAI-PMH and REST are open, free, and universal protocols for information retrieval on the web.
- **A1.2:** the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary
 - Metadata is publicly accessible and licensed under public domain. No authorization is ever necessary to retrieve it.
- **A2:** metadata is accessible, even when the data are no longer available
 - Data and metadata will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental programme defined for the next 20 years at least.
 - Metadata is stored in high-availability database servers at CERN, which are separate to the data itself.

REDMIX is oriented to maximize the accessibility of project data. The data itself is written by researchers directly into the publicly accessible, online database, powered by DSpace, that allows harvesting via OAI-PMH protocol. Each dataset (as described above) is individually managed for release to the public, making it viewable and downloadable once the researcher has determined that it is ready (i.e. fulfilled editorial criteria). Any embargoes will be determined on a per-dataset basis and will only apply until a dependent publication is released.

The REDMIX website (under construction as of this writing) features full explore-and-search tools for all data, including IIIF viewers for document images. Moreover, all data are available for download in raw and processed formats: TEI-XML for the former, JSON API, and PDFs for the latter.

3. Making data interoperable

Interoperability on the repository side is ensured by Zenodo. To be Interoperable:

- **I1:** (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
 - Zenodo uses [JSON Schema](#) as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as [Dublin Core](#) or [MARCXML](#).
- **I2:** (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
 - For certain terms we refer to open, external vocabularies, e.g.: license ([Open Definition](#)), funders ([FundRef](#)) and grants ([OpenAIRE](#)).
- **I3:** (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data
 - Each referenced external piece of metadata is qualified by a resolvable URL

The project operates at the intersection of multiple vocabularies and standards.

1. The first are archival metadata which are expected to comply with standards for archival data encoding and exchange in

- Europe and the Red Sea region.
- 2. The second layer of metadata is standard latitude and longitude geo-encoding using the APIs of governmental services.
- 3. The third layer of metadata are the keywords and concepts, so the team will make use of the standardized vocabularies.

TEI-XML has been chosen as the method for storing data as it is a proven, stable, community-accepted, and has the immediate benefit of providing a foundation for interoperability.

FAIRsharing will be explored to look for other relevant standards.

4. Increase data reuse

Licenses: To maximize reuse, REDMIX will assign the following license to each type of output:

- **Creative Commons BY (CC BY) license:**
 - Textual:
 - Reports;
 - Journal articles;
 - Books;
 - Consent form template;
 - Consent form (compiled).
 - Audiovisual - Recordings of workshops;
 - Visual - Photos;
 - Geospatial - Multilayer maps;
 - Tabular:
 - Database of sources (alternatively to the CC0 license);
 - Bibliographies.
- **Creative Commons 0 (CC 0) license associated to this Credit formula for data reusers: Cite as [Dataset XYZ, created by XXX, on (date), available at (DOI)] :**
 - Tabular - Database of sources (alternatively to the CC BY license);
- **GNU General Public License:**
 - Software.

On the repository side, Zenodo ensures some Reuse features (<https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>)

To be Reusable:

- **R1:** (meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - Each record contains a minimum of DataCite's mandatory terms, with optionally additional DataCite recommended terms and Zenodo's enrichments.
- **R1.1:** (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - License is one of the mandatory terms in Zenodo's metadata, and is referring to an [Open Definition](#) license.
 - Data downloaded by the users is subject to the license specified in the metadata by the uploader.
- **R1.2:** (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
 - All data and metadata uploaded are traceable to a registered Zenodo user.
 - Metadata can optionally describe the original authors of the published work.
- **R1.3:** (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards

Zenodo is not a domain-specific repository, yet through compliance with DataCite's Metadata Schema, metadata meets one of the broadest cross-domain standards available.

As mentioned before, REDMIX data will follow the "as open as possible as closed as necessary" principle. The REDMIX website database allows the team members to produce, validate, and publish individual datasets. There are some embargoes envisioned.

5. Allocation of resources and data security

ETHICS	<p>All issues concerning data security, anonymization, and data transfer have been thoroughly addressed in the Ethics document.</p> <p>The Ethics document will be deposited in the Zenodo REDMIX Community.</p>
COSTS	<p>Hosting by the university has a nominal charge currently covered by the ERC budget. Coverage for the nominal fee of the latter after the end of the ERC project is under discussion.</p> <p>Data stewardship costs are offered as in-kind support by the Open Science Unit at the University of Turin.</p>
BACKUP	<p>To ensure the integrity and security of REDMIX research data, there is a comprehensive backup plan: each team member will keep a synchronized backup of all project files and datasets on the shared REDMIX Google Drive that serves as a centralized repository for collaborative work and secure backups. Google Drive is used only for non-GDPR data.</p> <p>Two backup techniques will be implemented: a cloud backup on a project drive provided by the University of Turin, and a full backup on encrypted hard drives.</p>
LONG TIME PRESERVATION	<p>The long-term preservation of REDMIX data is at the heart of project strategy. The REDMIX database is driven by open-standard TEI-XML documents, making the project data independent of any technology that might be used to query or display it. The data is available through two access points (as described above), the REDMIX production database, managed with DSpace, and as raw data stored with Zenodo.</p> <p>In Zenodo, the same database of the digital archive will be uploaded and updated. This is done because Zenodo allows assigning a unique identifier to the database, effectively enabling versioning and preserving it over time.</p> <p>REDMIX outputs will be available on Zenodo indefinitely, in accordance with Zenodo's data storage policies (https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/), which are designed to ensure the long-term preservation and accessibility of deposited data:</p> <p>Versions: Data files are versioned. Records are not versioned. The uploaded data is archived as a Submission Information Package. Derivatives of data files are generated, but the original content is never modified. Records can be retracted from public view; however, the data files and records are preserved.</p> <p>Replicas: All data files are stored in CERN Data Centres, primarily Geneva, with replicas in Budapest. Data files are kept in multiple replicas in a distributed file system, which is backed up to tape on a nightly basis.</p> <p>Retention period: Items will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently the lifetime of the host laboratory CERN, which currently has an experimental program defined for the next 20 years at least.</p> <p>Functional preservation: Zenodo makes no promises of usability and understandability of deposited objects over time.</p> <p>File preservation: Data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system.</p> <p>Fixity and authenticity: All data files are stored along with an MD5 checksum of the file content. Files are regularly checked against their checksums to ensure that file content remains constant.</p> <p>Succession plans: In case of closure of the repository, best efforts will be made to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject-based repositories.</p>